

ON THE FACTORS FOR IMPROVING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN IN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASPECT

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Abstract. *Today, the participation of women in a number of socio-economic areas can be observed more and more. Therefore, this article provides opinions on the factors of increasing the social activity of women on the socio-economic front.*

Keywords: *gender relations, self-development, socio-economic sphere, social welfare, women, women's career, self-awareness.*

The issues of women's professional career, self-realization, social or economic development are of particular importance in traditional society. Here, gender equality, on the one hand, embodies the function of the ethnic and socio-cultural system, and on the other hand, it specifically opposes all kinds of modernization processes of the globalizing society.

If you look at history, you can witness that the last years of the 20th century were a period that contributed to the establishment of gender relations. And it is safe to say that even today its roots are operating without significant changes. And in this regard, there is a connection between the dynamics of the economy and the specific characteristics of the change of traditional ethnic institutions, behavior, values, and motivations, and the problem of a woman's performance of traditional roles becomes acute. This has contributed to the entry of many women into the labor market, where it has become the basis for a woman's self-awareness in career, business and outside the home, in the field of education, and in general socio-economic life.

It should also be noted that all aspects of women's social activity aimed at changing and renewing democratic processes and the spiritual and cultural life of society have been studied in the research works of scientists. In particular, A.E. Abdusamedov, F. Abdurahmonov, O.M. Abilov, B. Aliyev, S. Atamuratov, E. Kh. Bobomurodov, I. Karimov, T. Mahmudov, Q. Nazarov, I. Saifnazarov, A. Kadirov, A. Huseynova analyzed in various directions in scientific research. It should also be recognized that their research relies on methods of scientific knowledge such as dialectical, historical, logical, analysis and synthesis, complex approach, and content analysis.

In the conditions of today's market economy, increasing the economic activity of women requires taking special measures by the state and society, developing long-term plans and programs. It is necessary to remember that not all women have the opportunity to fully demonstrate their abilities and potential in the conditions of market relations based on competition and conflict of interests. "Who's the best?" does not allow everyone to realize their inner creative powers. In this case, it will be necessary to support enterprising women, to help them develop their "own work". Only a woman who owns private property is active in economic relations.

Changes in the economy of independent Uzbekistan and the development of small business gave women the opportunity to reveal their economic initiative and potential in the field of work. Economic changes and, as a result, the development of entrepreneurship allowed a woman to significantly expand her social functions, take a different position in society and economic activity, and open her own business that meets the needs of the market economy. This, in turn, was of great

importance in solving many employment problems. It is also worth noting that today the main participation of women in business is one of the main ways of self-realization in life. That is, at this stage, building a successful career or building a business is considered a value that determines success and happiness in life for men and women in modern society. However, the peculiarity of a woman's activity is that she tries to combine two main spheres of life - professional activity and family, because they are equally important.

In this regard, it is important to determine the qualitative changes in women's entrepreneurship in the region, as well as to study the level of emancipation, the socio-cultural and economic characteristics of the social group of women in the field of business and entrepreneurship. In this way, women's activity will be evaluated in terms of its network characteristics, obstacles, as well as the relationship between age and place of residence with specific characteristics of the activity.

Through this analysis, the structure of the social group of businesswomen can be clarified. One of the main categories related to the form of entrepreneurial activity is age. It defines the relevant views and attitudes that guide businesswomen in choosing forms of entrepreneurial activity.

In order to analyze this situation, it is appropriate to divide the social group of businesswomen into 4 age groups:

1st category - up to 29 years of age when the issues of getting an education, acquiring a profession, starting a family, having a child, or directing them to work are being decided;

Type 2 - women aged 30-40, characterized by more family orientation, self-awareness, professional growth;

Type 3 — the category of women between the ages of 41-51, characterized by a stable position, gaining work experience, and realizing one's potential in business;

Category 4 - women over 51 years of age, who want to realize themselves in the business and family spheres in accordance with the individual characteristics of work and family life, that is, usually include those who want to show their active aspects.

Above, mainly the opinions related to the business sector were expressed. At this time, it was considered necessary to express views in the direction of education and science, and on this basis, we mentioned the following.

As for the level of education, a certain relationship with age can be noted here. The younger the category of women, the higher the indicator of their higher education. Economic, legal, pedagogic, humanitarian and engineering-technical directions are lacking in the fields of education. Here, too, it is logical that the higher the level is, the more complex and larger the form of business organization will be. That is, the main value is not only the level of income, but also the reputation of the field of activity and the possibility of self-realization. Also, as a result of research on this topic, the analysis of questionnaires conducted among the social group showed that more than half of the women were previously skilled workers according to their education, for example, in educational institutions, in trade, in public services. In addition, it is clarified that adaptation depends on the specific characteristics of market relations: for example, older women perceive the difficulties of running a business worse, are less flexible about them, and are often under stress.

Entrepreneurship in the market has become the main image for women living in different regions of the republic. That is, for many women in the region, entrepreneurship in the market is

an additional source of income, in addition to the main job, for example, in the public sector of the economy. The main reason for such activity is, of course, the lack of financial resources at the main place of work, but at the same time there is a fear of losing a small but stable income.

Women emphasize the socio-cultural characteristics of the country, the gender stereotypes that they have to overcome, and, accordingly, the traditional character of the local mentality. In addition, they are hampered by the dual burden of work-family to compete at a high level with men in business.

The analysis of the social group allows to identify another field preferred by republican women for entrepreneurship — this is the service field, i.e. cosmetology, tailoring, creation of creative workshops, farming, cooking, child development centers and such as. A service industry that often requires less start-up capital. And also, unlike production industries, it includes the component of innovation, creativity, organization of business in its own way. It does not require the involvement of a large staff.

Due to socio-economic, cultural changes, changes in family and marital relations, modern women need to show more independence, earn their own income, and have the ability to provide for themselves and their children. admits. At the same time, a woman's business activity is aimed at managing her time in favor of maintaining many traditional views about the position of women in the country's society and finding a balance between work and family, innovation and tradition. Voluntarily limiting the scope of one's business activity to a certain extent is not an exception.

Today, in the modern socio-cultural reality of the country, women maintain their traditional attitude towards the dominant role of universal human values such as family, children, and family values. At the same time, the expansion of women's opportunities to participate in the life of society, increase their socio-economic activity, change their socio-cultural status, make it possible to fill their lives with additional content and introduce new directions. Therefore, during the development of civil society, changes of historical importance are being implemented to expand the participation of women in the socio-political, economic, spiritual and cultural life of Uzbekistan. In particular, the legal-normative framework for ensuring women's socio-economic activity was formed; a social system was established to ensure women's participation in economic, spiritual and cultural life; A social and moral environment supporting democratic values was created for active participation of women in the socio-economic life of the society. It is very important and important to reveal the socio-philosophical nature of these changes, to determine ways to further increase the socio-economic activity of women.

It is worth noting that, although there are political parties in the country that are implementing a number of measures to increase women's entrepreneurship and socio-economic activity, their scope, weight and influence on the improvement of women's political culture are still the requirements of the time. not at the level Currently, 40-44% of women participate in the activities of political parties. Instead of the conclusion of the opinions, it is appropriate to give the following points:

- The share of women in political parties reached 44%, in the field of higher education 40%, in entrepreneurship 35%;
- In May of this year, the Senate of the Oliy Majlis adopted the strategy to achieve gender equality by 2030. As stated by the President Sh. Mirziyoyev, as well as other priorities in this strategy, "creating decent work and living conditions for our loving mothers and sisters, who are

angels of grace in our lives, and pleasing them is not only the duty of leaders at all levels, but also first of all, it is a human duty."

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